

RELATIONSHIP MARKETING AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION: A STUDY OF GENDER ROLE (WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECTOR BANKS)

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Abstract

The modern commercial banks accomplish a number of roles. The entry of new banks both in public as well as private sector and the other financial institutions has enlarged competition. Banking is a customer-oriented industry. Customer satisfaction and relationship marketing are the new forms of strategies adopted by the banks to improve their working. The objective of the present study is to observe the differences of opinions of male and female customers on product quality, services and satisfaction provided to them by the banks. For this purpose, a sample of 200 customers was selected. Questionnaire of relationship marketing and customer satisfaction was administered on them and the results were tabulated using Mean, SD, T-ratio. The conclusion which was derived from the study is that, the customer satisfaction in both public and private sector banks was affected by the gender differences whereas there is no significance difference is found in relationship marketing of banks. The paper discusses the results and draws their implications.

Key words: Relationship Marketing, Customer Satisfaction, Banks

Introduction

Over the last few years, India's economy has been on a high growth trajectory creating unparalleled prospects for its banking sector. Most banks have enjoyed high growth and their valuations have appreciated significantly during this period. Looking ahead, the most pertinent issue is how well the banking sector is positioned to cater to continued growth (Sengupta 215).

In terms of ownership, commercial banks can be grouped into nationalized banks (majority ownership by The Government of India), regional rural banks and private sector banks (old and new, domestic and foreign).

Banking is a customer-oriented service. The customer is the king; therefore, customer is the main focus and customer service is the differentiating factor. Today, banks have to look much beyond just providing a multi-channel services platform for its customers (Jayawardhena and Foley 71).

When we talk about service sector, banks are very important. Banks helps in capital formation and

building a strong economic environment for smooth functioning of various financial activities. (Jadon, 2022)

Relationship marketing differs from other forms of marketing in that it recognizes the long-term value of customer relationships and extends communication beyond intrusive advertising and sales promotional messages. With the growth of the internet and mobile platforms, relationship marketing has continued to evolve and move forward as technology opens more collaborative and social communication channels. This includes tools for managing relationships with customers that go beyond simple demographic and customer service data. Relationship marketing was first defined as a form of marketing developed from direct response marketing campaigns which emphasizes customer retention and satisfaction, rather than a dominant focus on sales transactions. The overall goals are to find, attract and win new clients, nurture and retain those the company already has, entice former clients back into the fold, and reduce the costs of marketing and client service (Berry 239).

Relationship marketing can be applied when there are competitive product alternatives for customers to choose from and when there is an ongoing and periodic desire for the product or service. It involves the application of the marketing philosophy to all parts of the organization (Perrien 143).

The present commercial banking system in India has been classified into public sector banks, private sector banks, and foreign banks. A private bank is one that is owned and controlled by an individual or a group of people and this report personally to its management. In economics, the private sector, sometimes referred to as the citizen sector, is that part of the economy which is run by private individuals or groups, usually as a means of enterprise for profit, and is not controlled by the state. A public bank is that which is owned and controlled by the government and the decisions taken or the management is totally under the control of the government (Sathye 668).

Objectives

1. To study the difference between the level of customer satisfaction in the male and the female customers of both public and private sector banks.
2. To determine the difference between the customers of private and public sector banks at the level of relationship marketing.

Hypotheses

1. There will be a significant difference between customer satisfaction of the male and the female customers of public and private sector banks.
2. There will be a significant difference between the male and the female customers of public and private sector banks in relationship marketing.

Research Methodology

Quantitative approach and exploratory design to research was adopted to ensure the generalization of the result and due to the fact that the study tries to determine the associations among constructs in the framework as stated as a prerequisite to adopting the quantitative approach by and exploratory because the study seeks new insights into relationship marketing.

Variables

1. Customer satisfaction
2. Relationship marketing
3. Customer of public sector bank:
4. Customer of private sector bank:
5. Gender
 - (a) Male
 - (b) Female

Sample and Selection Criteria

Among the private sector banks, the customers of HDFC and ICICI are taken into the study, and out of the public sector banks, the customers of SBI and PNB have been studied for the present research. The sample consisted of 200 customers. 100 customers of public banks and 100 customers of private banks were selected on availability basis. The sampling is shown below graphically

Selection criteria

- 1) Two banks of each public and private sector were selected, namely S.B.I. and P.N.B. from the public sector and I.C.I.C.I. and H.D.F.C. from the private sector.
- 2) Age range between 35-65 years.
- 3) Informed consent of the customers.

Tools employed

Two questionnaires consisting of 20 items each were prepared in order to measure customer satisfaction and relationship marketing respectively.

Questionnaires of customer satisfaction and relationship marketing were prepared having 20 items each. Items in both the questionnaires were answered in 5 options namely: Not Experienced, Needs Improvement, Satisfactory, Good and Excellent which were scored as 1, 2, 3, 4, 5 respectively.

Statistical tools

Mean, SD, T-ratio were calculated for the analysis of the data.

Analysis and Results

Table 1: Mean, SD, SED, T-ratio and significance level of customer satisfaction and relationship marketing between the male and the female customers of public sector banks (N= 50):

Variables	Category	N	Mean	SD	SED	T	Sig
Customer Satisfaction	Male	50	60.26	7.66	1.48	1.09	.28
	Female	50	58.64	7.13			
Relationship Marketing	Male	50	56.22	6.92	1.40	-.54	.59
	Female	50	56.98	7.13			

*= significant at 0.01 level

** = significant at 0.05 level

Graph 1: Bar diagram representing the Mean scores of customer satisfaction and relationship marketing between the male and the female customers of public sector banks:

Table 2: Mean, SD, SED, T-ratio and significance level of customer satisfaction and relationship marketing between male and female customers of private sector banks (N= 50):

Variables	Category	N	Mean	SD	SED	T	Sig
Customer Satisfaction	Male	50	62.50	7.23	1.48	1.80	.07
	Female	50	59.84	7.52			
Relationship Marketing	Male	50	59.84	7.89	1.44	-.33	.74
	Female	50	60.32	6.40			

*= significant at 0.01 level

** = significant at 0.05 level

Graph 2: Bar diagram representing the Mean scores of customer satisfaction and relationship marketing between the male and the female customers of private sector banks:

Table 3: Mean, SD, SED, T-ratio and significance level of customer satisfaction and relationship marketing between the male and the female customers of private and public sector banks (N= 100):

Variables	Category	N	Mean	SD	SED	T	Sig
Customer Satisfaction	Male	100	61.38	7.49	1.05	2.04	.04**
	Female	100	59.24	7.32			
Relationship Marketing	Male	100	58.03	7.61	1.03	-.60	.55
	Female	100	58.65	6.95			

*= significant at 0.01 level

** = significant at 0.05 level

Graph 3: Bar diagram representing the Mean of customer satisfaction and relationship marketing between the total male and female customers of private and public sector banks:

Discussion

Table 1 reveals the Mean, SD, SED, T-ratio and significance level of customer satisfaction and relationship marketing between the male and the female customers (N= 50) of public sector banks. It was observed that there was no significant difference in the customer satisfaction among the male and the female (T=.28). Difference may be seen at the mean level of the male (M=60.26) and the female (M=58.64) customers in customer satisfaction. A minor difference was observed at the mean level of relationship marketing of banks among the males (M=56.22) and the females (M=56.98) whereas no significant difference was found between the male and the female customers.

It may be observed that no significant difference has been found between the male and the female customers of public sector banks in the customer satisfaction and relationship marketing. When calculated, difference was observed at the mean level and it was found that the customer satisfaction was higher among the male customers than the female customers in the public sector banks. It may also be observed that there is a difference in the relationship marketing, where female customers scored more than the male customers at the mean level indicating that the females are more satisfied with the marketing techniques followed by the banks in the public sector. At a significant level no difference was seen in the male and female customers regarding relationship marketing (Pahwa and Saxena 12).

Table 2 states Mean, SD, SED, T-ratio and significance level of customer satisfaction and relationship marketing between the male and the female customers of public sector banks (N= 50). It may be observed that there is no difference between the satisfaction level of the male and the female customers in customer satisfaction (TT=.07) and relationship marketing (TT=.59) at significant level. But at the mean level difference can be seen among the male (M=62.50) and female customers (M=59.84) in the customer satisfaction. Difference was also seen among the male customers (M=59.84) and the female customers (M=60.32) regarding the relationship marketing techniques followed by the banks.

It was observed that there is no significant difference between the male and the female customers in the level of customer satisfaction and relationship marketing techniques of the banks in the public

sector. Similarly, nosignificant difference was found among the male and the female customers in customer satisfaction though at mean level it was found that the male customers perceived significantly more satisfaction as a customer than the females. It may also be analysed in the mean scores that in the relationship marketing variable, the mean scores of the females are higher in comparison to that of the male customers. However, nosignificant differences were found among the male and the female customers in therelationship marketing of the banks(Patnayak and Swain 256).

Table 3 shows the Mean, SD (Standard Deviation), SED (Standard Error Difference), T-ratio and significance level of customer satisfaction and relationship marketing between the male and the female customers of private and public sector banks (N= 100) and level of significance achieved by the scores. It may be observed that there was a significant difference between the male and the female (T=.04) customers in the level of customer satisfaction but no difference was seen in the relationship marketing of the banks. A difference in the mean level may be seen in the customer satisfaction of the male (M=61.38) and the female (M=59.24) customers. At relationship marketing the difference in the mean level among the male (M=58.03) and the female customers (M=58.65) was also seen.

When the customer satisfaction among the male and the female customers was compared, it was found that in customer satisfaction there was a significant difference between the male and the female customers. At the mean level also, differences were found. The male customers derived greater customer satisfaction in comparison to the female customers whereas no significant difference was found in the relationship marketing of the private and public sector banks among the male and the female customers. According to the mean scores,the female customers derived greater satisfaction than the male customers in the relationship marketing of the banks, though this difference was not very significant.

The significant differences among the male and the female customers regarding their perception may be caused by several reasons. The male customers lay more emphasis on the variable of customer satisfaction as compared to the female customers. These differences result from the personality associated with gender. There are male customers who may be more experienced in dealing with the banks because they have been rating financial decisions in their families for a very long period. The male customers visit banks on a more regularly basis than the female customers. They are in direct contact with the working conditions and the employees of the banks and hence feel more satisfied (Neilson and Chadha 213). They are aware and informed in all banking-related issues hence they give more weightage to factors like loan rates, services offered, process time, investment opportunities, etc. The recent involvement of female customers in the banking activities makes them more demanding (Muniraju and Kumar 3). Female customers, however, have become an important market segment for the financial institutions but as they visit the banks less often, they are found to be more influenced by the marketing techniques like response from bank employees, goodwill and awareness of the bank in the social group, trust in the bank, execution of the campaigns, etc. The interpersonal relationship maintained by the male and the female customers might be one of the reasons for such a difference. More than the male customers the female customers are highly dependent on the word of mouth (Ketkar 1692).

Spathiset. al discussed the service quality on the basis of their customer's perceptions and analyses how gender differences affects the customer's perceptions of service quality dimensions such as effectiveness and assurance, access, price, tangibles, service portfolio and reliability. The results of an empirical study of 1,260 customers of banks generally support the hypothesis that gender affects service quality perceptions and the relative importance attached to various banking service quality dimensions. The paper provides important information for bank managers to use in developing operational, human resource, and marketing strategies, and in targeting those strategies in terms of the gender differences in quality perceptions among their customers (98).

Duffyyet. al observed that the aim of an empirical study of the service sector in US retail banking, was to establish the link between satisfaction and various recovery strategies. A total of 310 bank customers responded to a survey addressing customer demographics, the levels of satisfaction, the types of recovery strategies, and the service recovery of employees. Frequencies, chi-square analysis and correspondence analysis were used to analyse the data. The findings show no significant difference in recovery strategies or satisfaction by the customer's age, gender, or tenure with bank. However, the degree of customer satisfaction was strongly influenced by the type of recovery strategy used by the bank. The results indicate that recovery efforts are best directed toward empathic listening and fixing the problem rather than apologizing or making atonement (121).

Conclusion

It may be concluded from the findings that customer satisfaction in both public and private sector banks was affected by the gender differences whereas in relationship marketing of banks no difference was found among them.

Suggestions for improvement

1. More research variables may be added in order to get more details of the customers.
2. Training and development programs may be organized by the banks to deal with the components which require more emphasis.
3. Strong feedback mechanism should be developed by the banks in order to ensure continuous improvement in the policy systems of the banks.
4. This study is limited to few banks only, more banks from public and private sectors may be included in order to strengthen the results.

Limitations

Although the study was carried out with extreme enthusiasm and careful planning, there are several limitations, which are as follows:

1. The sample size was relatively small to generalize the results.
2. It is difficult to know if all the respondents gave accurate information; some respondents tend to give misleading information.
3. It was difficult to find respondents as they were busy in their schedule, which makes the collection of data very difficult. Consequently, the study had to be based on the availability of respondents.

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